

Implant level multiunit abutment the absolutely contraindicated approach an insight based on tolerances

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Abstract

Screwable implant prosthesis provide an indispensable solution to restore dental implants. Production in many times done by casting or by milling. Tolerances is an integral part of the production. Considering of this issue which result in significant effect on the implant is of paramount importance.

Keywords: dental implant, multi-unit abutment, Biomechanics, Tolerances, contact pressure, Titanium corrosion

Introduction

A golden description of the mechanical tolerances written by Corrado Poli stipulates: “A tolerance is a designer-specified allowed variation in a dimension or other geometric characteristic of a part. Proper tolerances are crucial to the proper functioning of products. However, the most common cause of excessive manufacturing cost is the specification by designers of too many tolerances or tolerances that are tighter than necessary” (1).

Misfit due to higher tolerances could be due

- Issues related to the volume
- Issue related to the relative 3D spatial position of the feature in the space in relation to the global coordination system

The misfit of the implant abutment setting in the case of the implant level multiunit will result from these issues

- The data acquisition whether done by digital or analogue method will result in higher discrepancy between the digital model and the real model which is beyond the scope of this paper
- The production had many aspects that results in deviation of the input CAD file from the manufactured prosthesis

Many companies produce the abutment level multi-unit abutment in a form that permit sliding of the components on each other providing the capability of good seating. While in the case of the implant level multi-unit abutments, the good setting is a matter of theoretical assumption (2)

Figure 1 Although the design on the right is more robust but it will result in highest possibility of the units' interferences

*Figure 2 The only method of producing perfect surface to surface connection between the abutment and the implant is the cementation method from **Straumann** where the multiunit prosthesis is cemented inside the patient mouth*

Figure 3 Tolerances could be due to change in position or volume

Many reported cases of fractured implant in the social media which presented as a challenging case, but in reality, these cases represent production of multiunit abutment and they are implant level and constructed using casting method or casing over titanium abutment where the process should be totally rejected.

Figure 4 implant level multi-unit abutment prosthesis will have many misfits and the gaps will exceed the permissible tolerances

Figure 5 implant level multiunit abutment necessitating removal of the part of the abutment to guarantee setting fitness.

The low temperature fusion ceramics should give us an insight about how the futile process of casting Chromium-Cobalt alloys over titanium abutment apart from the issue of the tolerances (3)

Figure 6 In some instances, the abutment is used directly during formal dental laboratory casting by dental technicians.

For such instances in the Figure 6, the abutment will be severely deteriorated due to the multiple processing of the abutments. I had seen a case in which the dental technician had cast chromium cobalt directly over the abutment and veneer it by high temperature fusion dental ceramic. In all the lab steps, the surface of titanium will be severely damaged affecting the fitting and resulting in already what could be called failed part. This is because the oxidation layer, in this case where the main alloy is a Titanium alloy and exposed to high temperature, is thick and brittle.

One of the limiting factors behind using titanium as core in the metallic dental prosthesis is that its veneering by dental ceramic is very limited and special ceramics with specific CTE and processing methods should be implemented (4).

Tolerances of implant and abutment which is reflected through the manufacturing process should be kept to the minimum level and only individually seated abutment in the implant if

we have an implant supported bridge is by tightening each abutment individually by which we could get surface to surface contact, otherwise we will get point to surface contact.

Reverse engineering of a design is not an impossible job, and many devices of the post-production inspection could be used to reverse engineer any product or verify the production accuracy. We think that the tolerances and dimensions must be included in the leaflet of any medical or dental product especially dental implants. As an end-user (the implant surgeons), I am not be interested in copying the design which as we say is not impossible to be done. And if a manufacturer wants to do so by copying another company design, it is a very easy job for him to be accomplished.

Figure 7 An example of casting Chromium Cobalt alloy over the Titanium abutment. Many dental technicians try to polish the lower part of the abutment to make more aesthetic which result is high amount of material to be removed

An important thing to be discussed and clearly disclosed is the absence of implant specifications, dimensions, and tolerances. We have conducted a study as we do abutment shrinkage by 0.005926mm (about 6microns) only in some part of the interface between the implant and abutment where the shrinkage happened only in the abutment. This is uniform dimensional difference and in the zero-tolerance model. The red line indicates only where the shrinkage had been done

Any metal that enters a furnace will have its surface to be deteriorated which leave it a highly irregular surface where contact will be multiple points instead of surface on surface (5)

Figure 8 The difference between machined using CNC on the right and another machining method (EDM) on the left is apparent although many consider the parts produced with EDM technology to have zero tolerances (6)

In different manufacturing technique of the customized abutment, the lab technician modifies the abutment to get shiny nice surface, where the gap between the implant and abutment will be highly irregular and the resultant aftermovement will be unpredictable resulting in tremendous possibility in fracture incidence. Ironically, we are becoming busy in showing the management rather addressing the issue that led to such disastrous result (7)

Figure 9 In many times we are seeing the management of the fractured connecting screw is toward the showing off the capability of the treating dentist rather than the addressing the real problem as we said

Figure 10 The noticing of the reported fractured abutment, implant or connecting screw without any paying attention to the manufacturing process of the abutment itself is highly myopic

Figure 11 The evaluation of any fracture in any implant part should be done with careful inspection of the abutment. Sadly, the concentration is only of the event without issuing a warrant for the manufacturing of the abutment (8)

The gap in the case of implant abutment connection will result in rotating swinging of the abutment inside the implant which result in exaggerated wear and tear between the implant and abutment as well as high possibility of the connecting screw fracture

In our current paper we want to introduce simple model of abutment implant mismatching

As a general rules, we should not use

- Zirconia abutment as the abrasion will be high
- Chromium cobalt alloys as it is hard and will cause corrosion as well as it will produce rough surface on smooth surface where the originally implant abutment connection should be smooth on smooth surfaces
- Multiunit abutment due to the tolerances issue as well as due to the

The issue of the irregularity of the heated abutment will be resulted in

- Damaging the implant internal surfaces releasing corrosion products from both abutment and the implant
- Soon or later the abutment will have its surfaces to be burnished and have these irregularities to be smoothed
- This gap will result in loss of the initial tight setting of the abutment inside of the implant. In many poor cases, the worst manufactured prosthesis will have initial tightening. This will result in totally different pattern of implant abutment connection response to the mechanical loading
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Figure 12 This is a disastrous dental laboratory work where the basic engineering rules had been neglected. This work will ensue higher failure rate including implant fracture or at least damage of the connecting screw fracture. The surgeon is the responsible person for any complication that could result from

Figure 13 Different responses of the implant abutment connection will happen in the case of casted abutment

Figure 14 The difference between the single contact point and surface to surface contact is need many aspects of the pure mechanics to be comprehended before accepting the casting of the Titanium abutments

The abutment in the Figure 14 would be initially deceive the dentist it had good tightening force after connecting screw turning inside, but with each loading loss of the material will release more Titanium result in higher misfit

Figure 15 The position is same but with significant differences

Figure 16 The red line will show clearly the effect of the reduced size of the abutment which will be slinked inside the implant if we have lessened volume due to futile dental lab work

The protruding points from the casted abutment will produce in reality multiple points, but for the matter of simplification we had chosen a design that reveal part of this issue

Figure 17 The change in in the contact will be followed by change in the arm of the resistance and force

It is important to consider the loss of the material during implant-abutment connection functioning (9). All the current assumption should be evaluated individually and

Methods

A simplified model had been used to demonstrate the effect of the misfit and high tolerances. We had selected a very tight tolerance relatively and the hex is in intimate contact with the implant. Although this is highly theoretical considerations, but it is used for comparisons of different designs. This is in high similarity to the design of Zimmer implant or C-tech implant as the manufacture of these systems implement 2 contact strategy between the abutment and the implant.

Figure 18 V-tech claims that dual contact abutment is a good feature

Figure 19 We had chosen very tight tolerances which far exceed the capability of the most advanced implant manufacturers. .005926 meaning the tolerances is about 3 microns in the case of implant and abutment which nearly impossibly to be produced. I see some implant surgeons restore the implant with a screw-retained prosthesis produced by an incorrect processing method.

Figure 20 We should consider these irregularities will be flattened fast and will result in more concentrated wear from the implant as well as higher release of titanium wear products

Figure 21 The tolerances in implant dentistry are a matter of guess and according to the knowledge of the authors, no company tells or shares their product tolerances or give even any clue about it

Figure 22 In many case the loss of material is evident with poor dental laboratory procedures

Figure 23 screw retained prosthesis is a trend that lead to incorrect decisions

Figure 24 no one could recognize the implant system type

Figure 25 Some part of the work is beautiful but the whole work eventually should be rejected

Results and discussions

Figure 26 The gapped model. The range of stain is less than the analog 2 pieces model

Figure 27 First and third principal strains here are higher in the implant and lower in the bone than in the zero-tolerance model the walls of the implant vent at the side of force application have nearly vanished and at the contralateral side are highest at the region of inlet without the involvement of the remaining region

Figure 28 Simple presentation of the effect of the tolerances. In case of rotation only small region of the hub and shaft will be in contact in the model B. When the tolerance is zero, that's mean all the region A will have a contact on both sides from the beginning of the deformation. The contact in the case A will be optimum and in full surfaces contact

In the case of tolerances more than zero at a region of the implant abutment contact, which is what will result in the casted abutment by some dental laboratories work, that's mean such triangle at both sides as shown in the Figure 28 could have a clear and obvious impact on the performance of the implant

In case of a tapered implant, this could be lessened we must emphasize that only 2 microns tolerance here is uniform, while in the case we had shown the previous pictures from the real prosthetic replacements where they had been done, the condition is the worst condition that is happened to an abutment with severe tolerances, which would guarantee failed implant.

The abutment has severely damaged and deteriorated chemically and mechanically after the direct casting of the Cr Co alloy over the Titanium abutment, then it had been entered the ceramic furnace multiple times during ceramic processing. These processes resulted in macro damage to the hub region of the implant which further necessitates doing polishing and grinding of the hub region by the lab technician to make it shiny with appealing appearance!!!

Figure 29 The same as we see in previous figure comment

Slice: Volumetric strain (1) Slice: First principal stress (N/m²) Slice: Third principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 30 3rd and 1st principal stresses go with the same previous comments.

The lesser distributions and higher values, double in compression indicate more corrosion effect especially fretting corrosion, which ultimately results in more release of the Titanium corrosion products in the peri-implant tissues. This might lead to a subsequent loss of bone and failure Contact pressure is an indispensable tool to correlate the current design to the corrosion that could result from the interaction between the modularities of the implanted devices

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 31 Less prominent second principal strain in the bone indicate less deformity sheer, and it goes with the previous results comments

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 32 Second principal stress goes with the second principal strain

Slice: Total displacement (m)

Figure 33 Displacement is greater than analog tight 2 pieces model

Slice: von Mises stress (N/m²)

Figure 34 These criteria demonstrate a close proximity to the previous findings

Figure 35 Volumetric strain is in close proximity to the Von Mises stress

Contour: First principal strain (1) Contour: Third principal strain (1)

Figure 36 Less concentrated strains at the walls of the implant vents

Slice: Volumetric strain (1) Slice: First principal strain (1) Slice: Third principal strain (1)

Figure 37 This the implant model without plastic investing cube

Slice: Volumetric strain (1) Slice: First principal strain (1) Slice: Third principal strain (1)

Figure 38 This figure goes with the previous findings

Figure 39 The same pattern as two pieces, with higher values and regions A and B are different from the other zero-tolerance model.

Figure 40 Region A and B indicates more shear than in the zero-tolerance model, where both is away from the intense compression of abutment with implant

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 41 The region of shear is in difference from those in the perfect in match model

Slice: Total displacement (m)

Figure 42 Higher displacement indicates less stiffness. In our model, we try to speak about each design criteria that we can cause weakening of the biomechanical performance if considered imprecisely. The current design of the implant in the markets may have negative points and also positive points at the same time that may lead to contradictory results

Figure 43 Nevertheless, there are many differences between the models of 2 microns and zero tolerance, the general features of the stress distribution is the same in both models Regions A and B which have no contact, have stresses due to the deformity

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 44 This model is different from the perfectly tight model

In the previous approach we had presented a model that is partially represent a great issue with high variations. Other variations should be investigated and analyzed

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as

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